

The Role of Components and Molecules of Periodontal Ligament in Orthodontic Tooth Movement

**Luay Thanoon Younis^{1*}, Mohd Masood², Faisal Ismail Elsayed Bahnasi¹,
Aida Nur Ashikin Abd Rahman¹ and Mohamed Ibrahim Abu Hassan¹**

¹*Faculty of Dentistry, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Sungai Buloh Campus, Sungai Buloh, Malaysia.*

²*La Trobe Rural Health School, La Trobe University, Bendigo, Australia.*

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. Authors LTY and FIEB designed the study and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author LTY managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Orthodontic treatment requires moving and aligning the teeth into a favorable position aesthetically and functionally. To achieve that, the teeth are subjected to forces to push them to their new position. Loading of force on the crown causes tipping of tooth, subsequently the periodontal ligament is compressed adjacent to the alveolar bone on the side toward which the force is directed. On the opposite side of the root, the periodontal ligament is stretched and undergoing tension. Blood vessels are compressed and blood flow is decreased on the compression side, hence less oxygen supply is received on that side. Compression and tension are triggering specific signaling factors and mediators, which create local environment and gradients to regulate remodeling of the periodontal ligament and bone for tooth movement. In this review, we highlight the structures and mediators released in the very narrow zone periodontal ligament during orthodontic tooth loading.

*Corresponding author: Email: drluay@uitm.edu.my;

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1. INTRODUCTION

The periodontal ligament (PDL) is a specialised connective tissue apparatus, located between the cementum of the tooth root and the bone forming the alveolar socket (alveolo-dental ligament) [1]. It acts as a shock absorber which transmits the biting forces to the alveolar bone. Cementum of the tooth root has intrinsic fibres (Ebner fibrils) run horizontally in a circle around the root and extrinsic PDL fibers (Sharpey's fibers) that are inserted into the cementum in one side and to the alveolar bone of the socket in the other side [2]. The extracellular matrix of PDL is composed of a network of fibrous structural proteins embedded in amorphous ground substance surrounding cells [3].

The ground substance of PDL is 70% water and is thought to have a role in absorbing stress loads applied on the tooth. Tissue fluids tend to increase within the matrix of the PDL ground substance in case of injury or inflammation. PDL matrix contains several noncollagenous matrix proteins released from the blood vessels passing through the ligament or produced locally by resident cells, these include alkaline phosphatase [4], proteoglycans [5], glycosaminoglycan, glycolipids and glycoproteins such as undulin, tenascin, and fibronectin [6]. The cells of periodontal ligament include fibroblasts, osteoblasts, osteoclasts, epithelial rests of Malassez, macrophages, monocytes, mesenchymal or stem-like cells, cementoblasts and odontoclasts, therefore, PDL considered as a cell reservoir for tissue proliferation and repair, homeostasis or regeneration [7-9]. Periodontal ligament also contains blood and lymphatic vessels, and nerve fibres. The width PDL ranges from 0.15 in the middle third of the root to 0.38 mm in the coronal and apical third of the root. It has been reported that PDL space decreases progressively with age or in certain bone disease conditions [1].

Regarding the aging of PDL, it has been found that the space between the alveolar bone and the cementum is gradually reduced over lifespan. Though bone formation decreases and bone resorption increases with aging, yet the PDL region tends to be thinner. This is probably attributed to the increased cementum thickness with age on the expense of PDL width. In addition, the reduced or loss of occlusal forces on aging result in osteoporotic alveolar bone and

atrophy of PDL fibres, hence a narrower PDL width [10,11].

Orthodontic forces result in structural changes of the dental tissues features. Cementum, PDL, bone, gingival tissues and bioactive substances (chemical mediators, enzymes, growth factors, neuropeptides and ligands) are collectively reacting and responding to the forces, subsequently periodontal tissues are re-organised and movement of teeth can be achieved [12,13].

The levels of these bioactive molecules may be affected (either increased or decreased) by certain medical conditions or medications taken. Unwanted disruption of the levels these molecules will aggravate or suppress the inflammation induced upon loading. If the normal scenario sequence of aseptic inflammation is disrupted, the orthodontic tooth movement may either accelerated, delayed or even halted. Hence, clinically these molecules can be used as targets to control or adjust the teeth movement to achieve the most favorable aesthetic outcome of orthodontic treatment.

In this article, we provide insights into PDL components and bioactive substances released within the PDL region during orthodontic tooth movement.

2. MAINTENANCE OF PERIODONTAL SPACE

PDL is occupying a space surrounded by two mineralised tissues (root cementum from one side and alveolar bone from the other side). This narrow space is maintained by molecules secreted by PDL cells that control calcification and avoid the ankylosis of tooth root with the adjacent alveolar bone throughout the life. The activities of these cells in secreting molecules of various types of proteins are increased during orthodontic movement. Certain mineralisation inhibitors such as matrix gamma-carboxyglutamic acid protein, a vitamin-K-dependant molecule; osteogenic transcription factor Msx2 and glycosaminoglycans or tripeptide-cementum attachment protein may have a pivotal role in maintaining the PDL space [14,15]. It has been found that balanced and reciprocal activities between bone sialoprotein and osteopontin may play a significant role in preserving and maintaining an unmineralized

PDL space. Osteopontin is expressed in the periodontium since tooth root development and has a potential role in periodontal tissue formation and maintaining the PDL - alveolar bone interface [16]. Due to its chemotactic activity in attracting osteoclasts precursor, osteopontin has been implicated in hastening tooth movement and root resorption during orthodontic treatment [17-19]. It has been reported that ERM has a role in the osteoclastogenesis of the alveolar socket, a process that subsequently leads to maintain the periodontal space during orthodontic treatment [20-22].

3. ADAPTATION OF PDL TO FUNCTION

Teeth are subjected to two types of forces: continuous, light and horizontal forces represented by soft tissues pressure from the tongue, cheeks and lips; and intermittent, heavy and vertical forces produced by chewing [23]. The PDL has the capacity to adapt to load changes. Increasing the loads for long term can increase markedly the width and thickness of the PDL fiber bundles. Contrariwise, a decrease in the load subjected on teeth leads to thinning of periodontal ligament and a reduction in thickness and number of the fiber bundles [24]. These load changes of the PDL are taking place concurrently with adaptive changes at the interface with cementum and alveolar bone [25].

4. PERIODONTAL LIGAMENT COMPONENTS IMPLICATED IN ORTHODONTIC MOVEMENT

Epithelial rests of Malassez (ERM) cells are remnants of the disintegrated Hertwig's epithelial root sheath, are found in the PDL space. TALIC et al. [26] conducted an animal study and found that ERM cells tend to proliferate and increase in size during experimental tooth movement. Orthodontic tooth movement causes an increased level of IL-6 released by human PDL fibroblast [27]. IL-6, in turn, promotes the proliferation and migration of ERM [28]. ERM proliferation is reflecting the potential role for these epithelial cells in accelerating the collagen turnover in the periodontal ligament during tooth movement [26-28].

It has been shown that ERM and PDL fibroblast have a reciprocal activity based on the singling and stimuli they receive. Periodontal fibroblasts produce collagen and a collagenase inhibitor

[29], while ERM produce latent collagenase which subsequently transforms to active collagenase by enzymatic cleavage [30]. ERM plays a role in the rejuvenation of collagen in the periodontal ligament. During PDL remodelling, collagenase of ERM degrades the collagen molecule into three-fourth and one-fourth peptide fragments, which then phagocytize by fibroblasts. Consequently, fibroblasts synthesize and secrete collagenase inhibitor which inhibits the active collagenase enzyme to form an inactive enzyme inhibitor complex [29,30].

It has been reported that the ERM contributes to the homeostasis of periodontium. ERM is thought to be involved in the induced tooth movement by increasing epidermal growth factor (EGF) production in PDL, preventing ankyloses and helping to repair root resorption areas by inducing cementogenesis [30,31]. EGF in return, stimulates ERM proliferation and maintains their growth and integrity [32]. EGF receptors are composed of transmembrane proteins that trigger tyrosine kinase intracellularly and initiate cellular events that activate cell division and remodelling/regeneration of periodontal tissue [33]. EGF secreted by the ERM is directly involved in osteoclastogenesis of alveolar bone through the suppression of osteoprotegerin, an important decoy receptor for RANKL [34]. Continuous release of EGF results in the upregulation of expression of monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP1), and hence, promoting the resorption of the adjacent alveolar bone, that ultimately leads to tooth movement, prevents ankylosis, as well as, maintaining the PDL space [20,30].

As part of its multifunction, ERM secrete inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins and enamel proteins such as amelogenin and amelin. Amelin, in turn, promotes the formation of bone matrix proteins, osteopontin, osteoprotegerin, BMP-2 and sialoprotein. These proteins participate in the regeneration and repair of periodontium [35-38]. Furthermore, it has been reported that disruption of periodontal integrity by trauma or orthodontic movement results in the expression of amyloid enamel protein APIN in ERM, which indicates that this protein may play a role in the initial phases of periodontal regeneration [39]. Mechanical forces induced by orthodontic appliance enhance the expression of bone matrix proteins, such as osteopontin, which stimulates resorption and repair of root and helps to prevent ankylosis [36,38,40].

4.1 Inflammatory Mediators, Cytokine and Transcription Factors

The orthodontic treatment induces an acute inflammatory response at its initial phase. In the early phase of tooth movement, leucocytes tends to migrate out of blood capillaries of periodontal ligament and producing cytokines which subsequently promote the excretion of prostaglandins and other mediators [41,42]. Prostaglandins, which are also released by ERM, specifically prostaglandin E₂, induce the recruitment and activation of osteoclasts and stimulate bone resorption/remodeling [20,30]. Application of orthodontic force stresses the extracellular matrix and deforms the nearby osteocytes of alveolar bone. Subsequently, this deformation opens the hemi-channels of the stressed osteocytes to release prostaglandins and recruit osteoclasts, which enhance orthodontic tooth movement [43,44]. Therefore, amount of prostaglandins produced plays a key role in orthodontic movement and also affects the rate of tooth movement [45,46].

Orthodontic forces enhance the production of various cytokines within the PDL space. Previous studies highlighted the role of IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α in bone remodelling [47,48,49]. The concentration of these cytokines is increased in the gingival crevicular fluid at the beginning stage of orthodontic treatment (12th and 24th hour) [50]. The cytokines are released by the infiltrating polymorphonuclear leukocytes and PDL cells in response to the applied forces [51]. The maximum level of the released molecules is attained three days after the application of orthodontic loading [52]. Cytokines induce local stimulation of osteoclasts which perform bone resorption [53,54]. The process involves nuclear transcription factor Kappa B (NF- κ B) (receptor activator of NF- κ B ligand, RANKL) which activates receptors of TNF- α (TNF-R1) at osteoblasts [55,56]. RANKL binds on a receptor at osteoclast named RANK. Subsequently RANKL activates osteoclasts to perform osteoclastogenesis [57]. Resorption is suppressed through prevention of RANKL binding for RANK by the decoy receptor osteoprotegerin, followed by the inhibition of osteoclasts differentiation [58,59].

This phase of alveolar bone resorption is shortly followed by decreasing the levels of secreted pro-inflammatory cytokines and reduction of blood vessels permeability [60]. As cytokines release is diminished in the tissues, the levels of

these cytokines in gingival crevicular fluid and the number of inflammatory cells is reduced after 7–10 days since the commencement of the orthodontic forces application [52,61]. The later events overlap with the beginning stage of regeneration/repairing of tooth supporting tissues, which lasts for around 9 days [62]. During the restoration of periodontal tissue, stimulation of osteoblasts takes place through the overexpression of various growth factors and interleukins which enhance the osteoid formation and suppress bone resorption [63,64].

During the early stage of orthodontic loading and after the initiation of early stage periodontal remodelling, there is a second wave of other cytokines such as IL-8 which was shown to have an increased level in the gingival crevicular fluid [6,45]. IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α stimulate the production of the other cytokines in monocytes, macrophages, epithelial cells, and fibroblasts of periodontium, this in turn, provoke the release of another wave of IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-2 and TNF- α [65,66].

High mobility group box 1 (HMGB1), a late inflammatory cytokine, is secreted by the periodontal ligament cells in response to mechanical stimuli [67]. It is also produced by stimulated dendritic cells, necrotic cells, macrophages and monocytes as a cytokine mediator of Inflammation [68,69]. On compression, HMGB1 provokes local inflammatory responses by stimulating the secretion of chemokines and cytokines from stressed cells [70,71]. The released HMGB1, would, in turn, stimulates human monocytes to produce and release TNF, IL-1 α , IL-1 β , IL-1RA, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, macrophage inflammatory protein (MIP)-1 α , and MIP-1 β in cultured periodontal ligament cells [70,71]. Furthermore, HMGB1 induces monocytes chemotaxis, macrophage migration and osteoclastogenesis [69,72]. HMGB1 is produced in the tension zone of PDL during orthodontic tooth movement, where it plays a role in tissues remodelling through stimulation of cells proliferation and formation of mineralized nodule in PDL cells [73,74].

Previous study has reported that periostin, a 90 kDa extracellular matrix protein, has an inhibitory effect on HMGB1 [75]. Periostin has a potential role in preserving the integrity of PDL collagen fibrils during orthodontic tooth movement, and its deficiency causes impairment of collagen

fibers degradation at the compression side of periodontal ligament, which obstructs orthodontic tooth movement [67].

Periostin is primarily expressed in connective tissues subjected to mechanical stress and stretch, such as skin, heart valves, PDL, bones and tendons [76-78]. Xu et al. [79] found that tensile stress load upregulates the levels of periostin in animals and human periodontal ligament fibroblasts during orthodontic tooth movement. Previous studies have also found that the periostin expression is regulated by transforming growth factor β , and that periostin promotes fibrillogenesis in PDL; and enhances migration of fibroblasts and osteoblasts, hence, it is essential for the PDL and bone remodelling during orthodontic loading [80,81].

4.2 Heat Shock Protein

Orthodontic force disturbs the blood supply of periodontal ligament and leads to hypoxia and ischemia in the tension zone during the early stages of tooth movement [82]. Consequently, these disturbances lead to the activation of cellular self-defense activities to reduce the stress and preserve the structure of periodontal ligament. It has been reported that heat shock protein (HSP) is released to serve this mission. HSP is upregulated in periodontal ligament during the early stages of orthodontic tooth movement [83-85].

Previous studies revealed that HSP70 has a regulatory role in the reduction of cytokines and RANKL expression and controlling the inflammatory periodontal ligament cell response to compression forces [84,86]. Inhibition of HSP70 resulted in significant reduction in cell division and proliferation and wound healing; while necrosis and apoptosis, osteoclastic differentiation and monocyte adhesion were highly increased in order to limit the tissue damage during orthodontic tooth movement [87].

4.3 Periodontal Ligament Blood Vessels

During orthodontic tooth movement, periodontal ligament blood vessels are significantly involved in the renovation of tooth surrounding tissues [3,88,89]. Several signals are generated after the compression of extracellular matrix which surrounds the cells of endothelia of blood vessels. These signals activate the restructuring

of existing vessels and also formation of new blood vessels in the periodontal ligament [90].

Mechanical forces cause distortion of the nerve terminals which in response they release vasoactive neurotransmitters [91]. In the periodontal ligament, most terminals are near blood-vessel walls. Subsequently, the released neurotransmitters activate the capillary endothelial cells receptors to bind circulating leukocytes, enhancing their migration out of the capillaries [92]. The migrating leukocytes secrete many signal molecules, including cytokines and growth factors, which play important role in the aseptic inflammatory reaction that stimulates periodontal ligament and alveolar bone remodeling and facilitates the movement of teeth [43].

4.4 Periodontal Ligament Cells Role in Osteoclastogenesis

It has been shown that periodontal ligament fibroblasts are adapted to the bacterial invasion and mechanical loading by secreting high amounts osteoclastogenesis-inducing factors. Hence, they possibly contribute to the escalated osteoclast recruitment observed during periodontitis and to orthodontic tooth movement [54]. It is believed that periodontal ligament cells regulate osteoclast differentiation through RANKL stimulation and osteoprotegerin inhibition, and also support osteoclastogenesis through cell-to-cell contact [93]. Cell-cell adhesion between periodontal ligament cells and osteoclast precursors significantly enhances the upregulation of genes for osteoclast differentiation and the eventual formation of osteoclasts [94].

4.5 Periodontal Ligament Cells Role in Osteoblastogenesis (Osteogenesis)

Periodontal ligament fibroblasts subjected to tensile strain were induced to express ephrin-B2 protein which in turn stimulate the osteoblasts of the alveolar bone and increase their osteoblastogenic gene expression at the tension sites during orthodontic tooth movement [95]. At the compression site of root, compressive forces induce periodontal ligament fibroblasts to produce ephrin-A2, while the expression of ephrin-B2 is down-regulated. Ephrin-A2 suppresses osteoblastogenic gene expression (RUNX2, ALPL) of osteoblasts and decreases the signs of osteoblastic differentiation at the compression sites [95,96].

4.6 Growth Factors

Orthodontic loading alters the flow of blood in the periodontal ligament and leads to the production of the angiogenic regulator, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), and tissue growth factor β (TGF- β) by the periodontal ligament fibroblasts and circulating leukocytes [97,98]. It has been shown that the level of anti-inflammatory cytokine TGF- β is higher at the tension side compared to the compression side of the root, which is probably attributed to its role in the process of osteogenesis and tissue formation at the tension side [3,41].

4.7 Enzymes

The inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) and neuronal nitric oxide synthase (nNOS) are three important enzymes released in the periodontal space during the early phase of orthodontic loading [99,100]. These enzymes are necessary for the production of nitric oxide (NO) which is an important regulator of bone remodelling [101,102]. Previous studies revealed that stimulation of NOS increases tooth movement, while inhibition of NOS reduces that movement [103,104]. The gene expression of synthase enzymes is controlled by pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , TNF- α) and anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-4, IL-10, TGF- β), which are secreted during tissues remodelling [105]. Orthodontic loading on animals have shown that iNOS is associated with bone resorption at the compression zone while eNOS is associated with the bone formation at the tension zone [100].

4.8 Regulating Occlusal Forces

The periodontal ligament has a pivotal role in controlling occlusal force associated with muscle spindles in jaw-closing muscles [106,107]. There are multiple receptors mediating the somatosensation in the periodontal ligament. These receptors include Ruffini endings and Merkel cells for mechanosensation processing. Nociception and itching are processed by the free nerve endings of A δ - and C-fibers [108-110]. Merkel cells of the epithelial rest of Malassez release neuropeptides which control the mechanosensation function [108,111]. Application of orthodontic forces leads to the constriction of the blood capillaries of the periodontal ligament in the pressure area that result in focal necrosis, with histological features

of hyalinization [112]. During this process, collagen fibers formation is regulated by ERM in order to promote adaptation to the orthodontic forces, homeostasis and maintenance of the periodontal tissues [12,30,38].

5. CONCLUSION

The periodontal ligament plays a significant role in the orthodontic tooth movement for being the field and source where many bioactive molecules are released in response to the orthodontic forces. Periodontal ligament is the first periodontal structure receives and reacts to the impact of loading. It is also important for being a pivotal part of theater for many molecular events which take place in order to achieve the orthodontic treatment. Clinically, several molecules produced by the periodontal cells upon orthodontic loading can be used as targets to accelerate or improve the movement of teeth.

CONSENT

It is not applicable.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

It is not applicable.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Nanci A, Bosshardt DD. Structure of periodontal tissues in health and disease. *Periodontology* 2000. 2006;40:11-28.
2. Niklas A, Proff P, Gosau M, Romer P. The role of hypoxia in orthodontic tooth movement. *Int J Dent*. 2013;2013:841840.
3. Li Y, Jacox LA, Little SH, Ko CC. Orthodontic tooth movement: The biology and clinical implications. *Kaohsiung J Med Sci*. 2018;34:207-214.
4. Groeneveld MC, Van den Bos T, Everts V, Beertsen W. Cell-bound and extracellular matrix-associated alkaline phosphatase activity in rat periodontal ligament. *Experimental Oral Biology Group. J Periodontal Res*. 1996;31:73-79.
5. Hakkinen L, Oksala O, Salo T, Rahemtulla F, Larjava H. Immunohistochemical

- localization of proteoglycans in human periodontium. *J Histochem Cytochem.* 1993;41:1689-1699.
6. Zhang X, Schuppan D, Becker J, Reichart P, Gelderblom HR. Distribution of undulin, tenascin, and fibronectin in the human periodontal ligament and cementum: Comparative immunoelectron microscopy with ultra-thin cryosections. *J Histochem Cytochem.* 1993;41:245-251.
 7. McCulloch CA. Origins and functions of cells essential for periodontal repair: The role of fibroblasts in tissue homeostasis. *Oral Diseases.* 1995;1:271-278.
 8. Lekic P, Rojas J, Birek C, Tenenbaum H, McCulloch CA. Phenotypic comparison of periodontal ligament cells *in vivo* and *in vitro*. *J Periodontal Res.* 2001;36:71-79.
 9. Menicanin D, Mrozik KM, Wada N, Marino V, Shi S, Bartold PM, Gronthos S. Periodontal-ligament-derived stem cells exhibit the capacity for long-term survival, self-renewal, and regeneration of multiple tissue types *in vivo*. *Stem Cells Dev.* 2014; 23:1001-11.
 10. Steigman S, Michaeli Y, Yitzhaki M, Weinreb M. A three-dimensional evaluation of the effects of functional occlusal forces on the morphology of dental and periodontal tissues of the rat incisor. *J Den Res.* 1989;68:1269-74.
 11. Lim WH, Liu B, Cheng D, Williams BO, Mah SJ, Helms JA. Wnt signaling regulates homeostasis of the periodontal ligament. *J Periodontal Res.* 2014;49:751-759.
 12. Wise GE, King GJ. Mechanisms of tooth eruption and orthodontic tooth movement. *J Den Res.* 2008;87:414-434.
 13. Baloul SS. Osteoclastogenesis and Osteogenesis during Tooth Movement. *Front Oral Biol.* 2016;18:75-79.
 14. Kirkham J, Brookes SJ, Shore RC, Bonass WA, Robinson C. The effect of glycosylaminoglycans on the mineralization of sheep periodontal ligament *in vitro*. *Connect Tissue Res.* 1995;33:23-29.
 15. Wiesmann HP, Meyer U, Plate U, Hohling HJ. Aspects of collagen mineralization in hard tissue formation. *Int Rev Cytol.* 2005;242:121-156.
 16. Foster BL, Ao M, Salmon CR, Chavez MB, Kolli TN, Tran AB, Chu EY, Kantovitz KR, Yadav M, Narisawa S, Millan JL, Nociti FH Jr, Somerman MJ. Osteopontin regulates dentin and alveolar bone development and mineralization. *Bone.* 2018;107:196-207.
 17. Singh A, Gill G, Kaur H, Amhmed M, Jakhu H. Role of osteopontin in bone remodeling and orthodontic tooth movement: A review. *Prog Orthod.* 2018;19:18.
 18. Standal T, Borset M, Sundan A. Role of osteopontin in adhesion, migration, cell survival and bone remodeling. *Exp Oncol.* 2004;26:179-184.
 19. Terai K, Takano-Yamamoto T, Ohba Y, Hiura K, Sugimoto M, Sato M, Kawahata H, Inaguma N, Kitamura Y, Nomura S. Role of osteopontin in bone remodeling caused by mechanical stress. *J Bone Miner Res.* 1999;14:839-849.
 20. Consolaro A, Consolaro MFM-O. As funções dos Restos Epiteliais de Malassez, o EGF e o movimento ortodôntico ou Por que o movimento ortodôntico não promove a anquilose alveolodentária? *Dental Press J Orthod.* 2010;15:24-32.
 21. Consolaro A. O conceito de reabsorções dentárias ou As reabsorções dentárias não são multifatoriais, nem complexas, controversas ou polêmicas! *Dental Press J Orthod.* 2011;16:19-24.
 22. Wang HM. Detection of lysosomal enzymes derived from pig periodontal ligament fibroblasts and their ability to digest collagen fibrils and proteoglycan. *Arch Oral Biol.* 1982;27:715-20.
 23. Denes BJ, Mavropoulos A, Bresin A, Kiliaridis S. Influence of masticatory hypofunction on the alveolar bone and the molar periodontal ligament space in the rat maxilla. *Eur J Oral Sci.* 2013;121:532-537.
 24. Niver EL, Leong N, Greene J, Curtis D, Ryder MI, Ho SP. Reduced functional loads alter the physical characteristics of the bone-periodontal ligament-cementum complex. *J Periodontal Res.* 2011;46:730-741.
 25. Naveh GR, Lev-Tov Chattah N, Zaslansky P, Shahar R, Weiner S. Tooth-PDL-bone complex: response to compressive loads encountered during mastication - a review. *Arch Oral Biol.* 2012;57:1575-1584.
 26. Talic NF, Evans CA, Daniel JC, Zaki AE. Proliferation of epithelial rests of Malassez during experimental tooth movement. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2003;123:527-533.

27. Kunii R, Yamaguchi M, Tanimoto Y, Asano M, Yamada K, Goseki T, Kasai KI. Role of interleukin-6 in orthodontically induced inflammatory root resorption in humans. *Korean J Orthod.* 2013;43:294-301.
28. Sako R, Kobayashi F, Aida N, Furusawa M, Muramatsu T. Response of porcine epithelial rests of Malassez to stimulation by interleukin-6. *Inte Endod J.* 2018;51: 431-437.
29. Ohshima M, Kuwata F, Sasai Y, Otsuka K, Suzuki K. Collagenase and collagenase inhibitors secreted by cultured human periodontal ligament cells. *J Nihon Univ Sch Dent.* 1993;35:109-117.
30. Silva BSE, Fagundes NCF, Nogueira BCL, Valladares JN, Normando D, Lima RR. Epithelial rests of Malassez: From latent cells to active participation in orthodontic movement. *Dental Press J Orthod.* 2017; 22:119-125.
31. Lindskog S, Blomlof L, Hammarstrom L. Evidence for a role of odontogenic epithelium in maintaining the periodontal space. *J Clin Periodontol.* 1988;15(6):371-373.
32. Thesleff I. Epithelial cell rests of Malassez bind epidermal growth factor intensely. *J Periodontal Res.* 1987;22:419-421.
33. Carpenter G. Receptors for epidermal growth factor and other polypeptide mitogens. *Ann Rev Biochem.* 1987;56:881-914.
34. Zhang X, Tamasi J, Lu X, Zhu J, Chen H, Tian X, Lee TC, Threadgill DW, Kream BE, Kang Y, Partridge NC, Qin L. Epidermal growth factor receptor plays an anabolic role in bone metabolism *in vivo*. *J Bone Miner Res.* 2011;26:1022-1034.
35. King GN, Hughes FJ. Bone morphogenetic protein-2 stimulates cell recruitment and cementogenesis during early wound healing. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2001;28:465-475.
36. Hasegawa N, Kawaguchi H, Ogawa T, Uchida T, Kurihara H. Immunohistochemical characteristics of epithelial cell rests of Malassez during cementum repair. *J Periodontal Res.* 2003; 38:51-56.
37. Wang Y, Lv L, Yu X, Zhang T, Li S. The characteristics of epithelial cell rests of Malassez during tooth eruption of development mice. *J Mol Histol.* 2014;45: 1-10.
38. Xiong J, Gronthos S, Bartold PM. Role of the epithelial cell rests of Malassez in the development, maintenance and regeneration of periodontal ligament tissues. *Periodontol 2000.* 2013;63:217-233.
39. Nishio C, Wazen R, Kuroda S, Moffatt P, Nanci A. Disruption of periodontal integrity induces expression of apin by epithelial cell rests of Malassez. *J Periodontal Res.* 2010;45:709-713.
40. Rincon JC, Young WG, Bartold PM. The epithelial cell rests of Malassez--a role in periodontal regeneration? *J Periodontal Res.* 2006;41:245-52.
41. Garlet TP, Coelho U, Silva JS, Garlet GP. Cytokine expression pattern in compression and tension sides of the periodontal ligament during orthodontic tooth movement in humans. *Eur J Oral Sci.* 2007;115:355-62.
42. Nimeri G, Kau CH, Abou-Kheir NS, Corona R. Acceleration of tooth movement during orthodontic treatment--a frontier in orthodontics. *Prog Orthod.* 2013;14:42.
43. Krishnan V, Davidovitch Z. On a path to unfolding the biological mechanisms of orthodontic tooth movement. *J Dent Res.* 2009;88:597-608.
44. Caglaroglu M, Erdem A. Histopathologic investigation of the effects of prostaglandin E2 administered by different methods on tooth movement and bone metabolism. *Korean J Orthod.* 2012;42:118-128.
45. Leiker BJ, Nanda RS, Currier GF, Howes RI, Sinha PK. The effects of exogenous prostaglandins on orthodontic tooth movement in rats. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 1995;108:380-388.
46. Kouskoura T, Katsaros C, von Gunten S. The potential use of pharmacological agents to modulate orthodontic tooth movement (OTM). *Front Physiol.* 2017; 8:67.
47. Blaschke M, Koepf R, Cortis J, Komrakova M, Schieker M, Hempel U, Siggekow H. IL-6, IL-1beta, and TNF-alpha only in combination influence the osteoporotic phenotype in Crohn's patients via bone formation and bone resorption. *Adv Clin Exp Med.* 2018;27:45-56.
48. Garcia-Lopez S, Villanueva R, Meikle MC. Alterations in the synthesis of IL-1beta, TNF-alpha, IL-6, and their downstream targets RANKL and OPG by mouse

- calvarial osteoblasts *in vitro*: Inhibition of bone resorption by cyclic mechanical strain. *Front Endocrinol.* 2013;4:160.
49. Kwan Tat S, Padrines M, Theoleyre S, Heymann D, Fortun Y. IL-6, RANKL, TNF-alpha/IL-1: Interrelations in bone resorption pathophysiology. *Cytokine Growth Factor Rev.* 2004;15:49-60.
 50. Dudic A, Kiliaridis S, Mombelli A, Giannopoulou C. Composition changes in gingival crevicular fluid during orthodontic tooth movement: comparisons between tension and compression sides. *Eur J Oral Sci.* 2006;114:416-422.
 51. Feller L, Khammissa RA, Schechter I, Thomadakis G, Fourie J, Lemmer J. Biological Events in Periodontal Ligament and Alveolar Bone Associated with Application of Orthodontic Forces. *Scientific World Journal.* 2015;876509.
 52. Alhashimi N, Frithiof L, Brudvik P, Bakhiet M. Orthodontic tooth movement and de novo synthesis of proinflammatory cytokines. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2001;119:307-312.
 53. Kitaura H, Kimura K, Ishida M, Sugisawa H, Kohara H, Yoshimatsu M, Takano-Yamamoto. Effect of cytokines on osteoclast formation and bone resorption during mechanical force loading of the periodontal membrane. *Scientific World Journal.* 2014;2014:617032.
 54. Sokos D, Everts V, de Vries TJ. Role of periodontal ligament fibroblasts in osteoclastogenesis: A review. *J Periodontal Res.* 2015;50:152-159.
 55. Azuma Y, Kaji K, Katogi R, Takeshita S, Kudo A. Tumor necrosis factor-alpha induces differentiation of and bone resorption by osteoclasts. *J Biol Chem.* 2000;275:4858-4864.
 56. Kitaura H, Yoshimatsu M, Fujimura Y, Eguchi T, Kohara H, Yamaguchi A, Yoshida N. An anti-c-Fms antibody inhibits orthodontic tooth movement. *J Dent Res.* 2008;87:396-400.
 57. Kobayashi K, Takahashi N, Jimi E, Udagawa N, Takami M, Kotake S, Nakagawa N, Kinoshita M, Yamaguchi K, Shima N, Yasuda H, Morinaga T, Higashio K, Martin TJ, Suda T. Tumor necrosis factor alpha stimulates osteoclast differentiation by a mechanism independent of the ODF/RANKL-RANK interaction. *J Exp Med.* 2000;191:275-286.
 58. Lacey DL, Timms E, Tan HL, Kelley MJ, Dunstan CR, Burgess T, Elliott R, Colombero A, Elliott G, Scully S, Hsu H, Sullivan J, Hawkins N, Davy E, Capparelli C, Eli A, Qian YX, Kaufman S, Sarosi I, Shalhoub V, Senaldi G, Guo J, Delaney J, Boyle WJ. Osteoprotegerin ligand is a cytokine that regulates osteoclast differentiation and activation. *Cell.* 1998; 93:165-176.
 59. Shalhoub V, Faust J, Boyle WJ, Dunstan CR, Kelley M, Kaufman S, Scully S, Van G, Lacey DL. Osteoprotegerin and osteoprotegerin ligand effects on osteoclast formation from human peripheral blood mononuclear cell precursors. *J Cell Biochem.* 1999;72:251-261.
 60. Meikle MC. The tissue, cellular, and molecular regulation of orthodontic tooth movement: 100 years after Carl Sandstedt. *Eur J Orthod.* 2006;28(3):221-240.
 61. Uematsu S, Mogi M, Deguchi T. Interleukin (IL)-1 beta, IL-6, tumor necrosis factor-alpha, epidermal growth factor, and beta 2-microglobulin levels are elevated in gingival crevicular fluid during human orthodontic tooth movement. *J Dent Res.* 1996;75:562-567.
 62. Hill PA. Bone remodelling. *Br J Orthod.* 1998;25:101-7.
 63. Kapoor P, Kharbanda OP, Monga N, Miglani R, Kapila S. Effect of orthodontic forces on cytokine and receptor levels in gingival crevicular fluid: A systematic review. *Prog Orthod.* 2014;15:65.
 64. Yue Y, Chen Z, Xie B, Yao HL. Expression of vascular endothelial growth factor in periodontal tissues during orthodontic tooth movement and its role in bone remodeling. *Shanghai Kou Qiang Yi Xue.* 2018;27: 18-21.
 65. Basaran G, Ozer T, Kaya FA, Hamamci O. Interleukins 2, 6, and 8 levels in human gingival sulcus during orthodontic treatment. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2006;130:7.e1-6.
 66. Ren Y, Vissink A. Cytokines in crevicular fluid and orthodontic tooth movement. *Eur J Oral Sci.* 2008;116:89-97.
 67. Li J, Feng W, Liu B, Sun B, Han X, Du J, Sun J, Yimi, Cui J, Guo J, Kudo A, Amizuka N, Li M. Altered distribution of HMGB1 in the periodontal ligament of periostin-deficient mice subjected to

- Waldo's orthodontic tooth movement. *J Mol Histol.* 2015;46:303-311.
68. Wang H, Bloom O, Zhang M, Vishnubhakat JM, Ombrellino M, Che J, Frazier A, Yang H, Ivanova S, Borovikova L, Manogue KR, Faist E, Abraham E, Andersson J, Andersson U, Molina PE, Abumrad NN, Sama A, Tracey KJ. HMG-1 as a late mediator of endotoxin lethality in mice. *Science.* 1999;285:248-251.
 69. Kanzaki H, & Nakamura, Y. Orthodontic tooth movement and HMGB1. *J Oral Biosci.* 2018;60:49-53.
 70. Andersson U, Wang H, Palmblad K, Aveberger AC, Bloom O, Erlandsson-Harris H, Janson A, Kokkola R, Zhang M, Yang H, Tracey KJ. High mobility group 1 protein (HMG-1) stimulates proinflammatory cytokine synthesis in human monocytes. *J Exp Med.* 2000; 192:565-570.
 71. Yang H, Wang H, Tracey KJ. HMG-1 rediscovered as a cytokine. *Shock.* 2001;15:247-253.
 72. Wolf M, Lossdorfer S, Craveiro R, Gotz W, Jager A. Regulation of macrophage migration and activity by high-mobility group box 1 protein released from periodontal ligament cells during orthodontically induced periodontal repair: An *in vitro* and *in vivo* experimental study. *J Orofac Orthop.* 2013;74:420-434.
 73. Wolf M, Lossdorfer S, Kupper K, Jager A. Regulation of high mobility group box protein 1 expression following mechanical loading by orthodontic forces *in vitro* and *in vivo*. *Eur J Orthod.* 2014;36:624-31.
 74. Wolf M, Lossdorfer S, Romer P, Craveiro RB, Deschner J, Jager A. Anabolic properties of high mobility group box protein-1 in human periodontal ligament cells *in vitro*. *Mediators Inflamm.* 2014; 347585.
 75. Cui J, Li J, Wang W, Han X, Du J, Sun J, Feng W, Liu B, Liu H, Amizuka N, Li M. The effect of calcitriol on high mobility group box 1 expression in periodontal ligament cells during orthodontic tooth movement in rats. *J Mol Histol.* 2016; 47:221-8.
 76. Takeshita S, Kikuno R, Tezuka K, Amann E. Osteoblast-specific factor 2: Cloning of a putative bone adhesion protein with homology with the insect protein fasciclin I. *Biochem J.* 1993;294 (Pt 1):271-8.
 77. Norris RA, Borg TK, Butcher JT, Baudino TA, Banerjee I, Markwald RR. Neonatal and adult cardiovascular pathophysiological remodeling and repair: developmental role of periostin. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 2008;1123:30-40.
 78. Bonnet N, Garnero P, Ferrari S. Periostin action in bone. *Mol Cell Endocrinol.* 2016; 432:75-82.
 79. Xu HY, Nie EM, Deng G, Lai LZ, Sun FY, Tian H, Fanh FC, Zou YG, Wu BL, Ou-Yang J. Periostin is essential for periodontal ligament remodeling during orthodontic treatment. *Mol Med Rep.* 2017; 15:1800-1806.
 80. Du J, Li M. Functions of Periostin in dental tissues and its role in periodontal tissues' regeneration. *Cell Mol Life Sci.* 2017;74: 4279-86.
 81. Rangiani A, Jing Y, Ren Y, Yadav S, Taylor R, Feng JQ. Critical roles of periostin in the process of orthodontic tooth movement. *Eur J Orthod.* 2016;38: 373-8.
 82. Davidovitch Z, Nicolay OF, Ngan PW, Shanfeld JL. Neurotransmitters, cytokines, and the control of alveolar bone remodeling in orthodontics. *Dent Clin North Am.* 1988;32:411-435.
 83. Arai C, Nomura Y, Ishikawa M, Noda K, Choi JW, Yashiro Y, Hanada N, Nakamura Y. HSPA1A is upregulated in periodontal ligament at early stage of tooth movement in rats. *Histochemistry and Cell Biology.* 2010;134:337-343.
 84. Mitsushashi M, Yamaguchi M, Kojima T, Nakajima R, Kasai K. Effects of HSP70 on the compression force-induced TNF-alpha and RANKL expression in human periodontal ligament cells. *Inflammation Research.* 2011;60:187-194.
 85. Baba S, Kuroda N, Arai C, Nakamura Y, Sato T. Immunocompetent cells and cytokine expression in the rat periodontal ligament at the initial stage of orthodontic tooth movement. *Archives of Oral Biology.* 2011;56:466-473.
 86. Marciniak J, Lossdorfer S, Kirschneck C, Deschner J, Jager A, Wolf M. Heat shock protein 70 dampens the inflammatory response of human PDL cells to mechanical loading *in vitro*. *J Periodontal Res;* 2019. DOI: 10.1111/jre.12648. [Epub ahead of print]

87. Wolf M, Marciniak J, Lossdorfer S, Kirschneck C, Brauner I, Gotz W, Jager A. Role of HSP70 protein in human periodontal ligament cell function and physiology. *Ann Anat.* 2019;221:76-83.
88. Kitase Y, Yokozeki M, Fujihara S, Izawa T, Kuroda S, Tanimoto K, Moriyama K, Tanaka E. Analysis of gene expression profiles in human periodontal ligament cells under hypoxia: The protective effect of CC chemokine ligand 2 to oxygen shortage. *Arch Oral Biol.* 2009;54:618-624.
89. Jiang N, Guo W, Chen M, Zheng Y, Zhou J, Kim SG, Embree MC, Songhee Song K, Marao HF, Mao JJ. Periodontal Ligament and Alveolar Bone in Health and Adaptation: Tooth Movement. *Front Oral Biol.* 2016;18:1-8.
90. Niklas A, Proff P, Gosau M, Romer P. The role of hypoxia in orthodontic tooth movement. *Int J Dent.* 2013;2013:841840.
91. Davidovitch Z. Tooth movement. *Crit Rev Oral Biol Med.* 1991;2:411-450.
92. Lew KK. Orthodontically induced microvascular injuries in the tension zone of the periodontal ligament. *J Nihon Univ Sch Dent.* 1989;31:493-501.
93. Kanzaki H, Chiba M, Shimizu Y, Mitani H. Dual regulation of osteoclast differentiation by periodontal ligament cells through RANKL stimulation and OPG inhibition. *J Dent Res.* 2001;80:887-891.
94. Bloemen V, Schoenmaker T, de Vries TJ, Everts V. Direct cell-cell contact between periodontal ligament fibroblasts and osteoclast precursors synergistically increases the expression of genes related to osteoclastogenesis. *J Cell Physiol.* 2010;222:565-573.
95. Diercke K, Sen S, Kohl A, Lux CJ, Erber R. Compression-dependent up-regulation of ephrin-A2 in PDL fibroblasts attenuates osteogenesis. *J Dent Res.* 2011;90:1108-1115.
96. Sen S, Diercke K, Zingler S, Lux CJ, Erber R. Compression induces Ephrin-A2 in PDL fibroblasts via c-fos. *J Dent Res.* 2015;94:464-472.
97. Yoshino H, Morita I, Murota SI, Ishikawa I. Mechanical stress induces production of angiogenic regulators in cultured human gingival and periodontal ligament fibroblasts. *J Periodontal Res.* 2003;38:405-410.
98. Morandini AC, Sipert CR, Ramos-Junior ES, Brozoski DT, Santos CF. Periodontal ligament and gingival fibroblasts participate in the production of TGF-beta, interleukin (IL)-8 and IL-10. *Braz Oral Res.* 2011;25:157-162.
99. D'Attilio M, Di Maio F, D'Arcangela C, Filippi MR, Felaco M, Lohinai Z, Festa F, Perinetti G. Gingival endothelial and inducible nitric oxide synthase levels during orthodontic treatment: A cross-sectional study. *Angle Orthod.* 2004;74:851-858.
100. Nilforoushan D, Manolson MF. Expression of nitric oxide synthases in orthodontic tooth movement. *Angle Orthod.* 2009;79:502-508.
101. van't Hof RJ, Ralston SH. Nitric oxide and bone. *Immunology.* 2001;103:255-261.
102. Chae HJ, Park RK, Chung HT, Kang JS, Kim MS, Choi DY, Bang BG, Kim HR. Nitric oxide is a regulator of bone remodelling. *J Pharm Pharmacol.* 1997;49:897-902.
103. Diravidamani K, Sivalingam SK, Agarwal V. Drugs influencing orthodontic tooth movement: An overall review. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci.* 2012;4(Suppl 2): 299S-303S.
104. Karthi M, Anbushevan GJ, Senthilkumar KP, Tamizharsi S, Raja S, Prabhakar K. NSAIDs in orthodontic tooth movement. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci.* 2012;4(Suppl 2): 304S-306S.
105. Ambe K, Watanabe H, Takahashi S, Nakagawa T, Sasaki J. Production and physiological role of NO in the oral cavity. *Jpn Dent Sci Rev.* 2016;52:14-21.
106. Lund JP, Kolta A. Generation of the central masticatory pattern and its modification by sensory feedback. *Dysphagia.* 2006;21:167-174.
107. Westberg KG, Kolta A. The trigeminal circuits responsible for chewing. *Int Rev Neurobiol.* 2011;97:77-98.
108. Tadokoro O, Maeda T, Heyeraas KJ, Vandevska-Radunovic V, Kozawa Y, Hals Kvinnsland I. Merkel-like cells in Malassez epithelium in the periodontal ligament of cats: an immunohistochemical, confocal-laser scanning and immuno electron-microscopic investigation. *J Periodontal Res.* 2002;37:456-463.
109. Maeda T, Ochi K, Nakakura-Ohshima K, Youn SH, Wakisaka S. The Ruffini ending as the primary mechanoreceptor in the

- periodontal ligament: Its morphology, cytochemical features, regeneration, and development. Crit Rev Oral Biol Med. 1999;10:307-327.
110. Byers MR. Sensory innervation of periodontal ligament of rat molars consists of unencapsulated Ruffini-like mechanoreceptors and free nerve endings. J Comp Neurol. 1985;231:500-518.
111. Kobayashi M, Horinuki E. Neural mechanisms of nociception during orthodontic treatment. J Oral Sci. 2017; 59:167-171.
112. Von Bohl M, Kuijpers-Jagtman AM. Hyalinization during orthodontic tooth movement: A systematic review on tissue reactions. Eur J Orthod. 2009;31:30-36.

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